

HackRF One Sweep Mode - A quick Introduction

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Abstract: HackRF is a software defined radio. The supported range is 1 MHz to 6 GHz. A scan of the entire supported range takes just 1 second.

Keywords: API, GitHub, Radio, Rapid, Scan, Swisscom, USB

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2017 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170622> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

It's a bit of time I own an *HackRF One*. And I had a lot of fun with it. *HackRF* [1] is a *Software Defined Radio*, a hardware platform capable of receive/transmit signals in a frequency range between 1 MHz and 6 GHz.

With the last firmware review (2017.02.1), HackRF received the capacity to *scan a wide range of frequencies*, rapidly retuning the radio clock (before that upgrade, the retuning had to be made externally). This function, called *Sweep Mode*, scans the entire supported range (1-6000 MHz) in less than 1s; more precisely, HackRF is capable to scan at a rate of 8 GHz/s, all for ~300\$, thanks to *Michael Ossmann* [2].

3. Preparation

First make sure to have the newest firmware:

```
[175468.801248] usb 2-1.5: new high-speed USB
device number 5 using ehci-pci
[175468.910224] usb 2-1.5: New USB device
found, idVendor=1d50, idProduct=6089
[175468.910228] usb 2-1.5: New USB device
strings: Mfr=1, Product=2, SerialNumber=4
[175468.910230] usb 2-1.5: Product: HackRF
One
[175468.910232] usb 2-1.5: Manufacturer:
Great Scott Gadgets
[175468.910234] usb 2-1.5: SerialNumber:
00000000000000457863c8256b511f
[175468.912066] hackrf 2-1.5:1.0: Board ID:
02
[175468.912069] hackrf 2-1.5:1.0: Firmware
version: 2017.02.1
[175468.912239] hackrf 2-1.5:1.0: Registered
as swradio0
[175468.912357] hackrf 2-1.5:1.0: Registered
as swradio1
[175468.912360] hackrf 2-1.5:1.0: SDR API is
```

still slightly experimental and functionality changes may follow

Then, install some SDR or signal analysis/manipulation tools, like gnuradio, gqrx, Audacity, rtl_*, and so on.

4. What can we do

4.1. FM Radio Broadcaster around

The yellow lines “vibrating” – frequency modulation – between the 92-108 MHz:

Figure: Radio Broadcasting with a Spectrum Analyzer

4.2. Well-known Bands

Here we can see the FDD downlink bands used by Salt – small line around 925 MHz – and the two 15 MHz wide of Sunrise and Swisscom – 930-960 MHz:

Figure: 900 MHz band

4.3. Fingerprint on RF Spectrum

Take a look at the whole supported spectrum:

Figure: Full Spectrum

4.4. Hunting Signals

To find out which frequency is used by a generic device, scan the spectrum until a difference is noted:

Figure: Full Spectrum

As second step we can restrict the range:

Figure: Restricted range

As last step we can restrict analysis center the device on the identified frequency:

Figure: Tuning the Signal

At the end, once recorded, we can pass the signal to other tools like Audacity, gnuradio, or – in this case – `rtl_433`:

```
rcc@ubunthin:~$ rtl_433 -f 434418000 -a -r
gqrx_20170612_165837_434418000.wav
...
Test mode active. Reading samples from file:
gqrx_20170612_165837_434418000.wav
Input format: uint8
*** signal_start = -9991, signal_end = 511495
signal_len = 521486, pulses = 3
Iteration 1. t: 215269 min: 70940 (2)
max: 359599 (1) delta 656265929
Iteration 2. t: 215269 min: 70940 (2)
max: 359599 (1) delta 0
Pulse coding: Short pulse length 70940 - Long
pulse length 359599

Short distance: 2, long distance: 0, packet
distance: 2

p_limit: 215269
bitbuffer:: Number of rows: 3
[00] {1} 00 : 0
[01] {1} 00 : 0
[02] {1} 80 : 1
Test mode file issued 8 packets
```

5. External Links

- [1] <https://github.com/mossmann/hackrf/wiki/HackRF-One>
- [2] <http://www.ossmann.com/mike/>